

Jack London's "Martin Eden" : Not everything you aspire to can be truly yours

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Abstract: Jack London is one of the great writers of all time. There is no booklover who has not read his books. The novels written by him attract people from all over the world. Especially his "Martin Eden" deserves special attention. This book is still a lantern for dried up souls, as it motivates to act.

Keywords: Martin Eden, poor, society, motivation, poems, elite, Ruth, love, true

American novelist and short-story writer Jack London, who is best-known for *The Call of the Wild* and *White Fang* mostly tried to describe his life in his novels and stories. It is hard to realise which part of his biography is written in his certain story or novel. After reading his works every reader can feel absolutely vice versa feelings and thoughts: if someone feels sorrow for characters, another person can feel anger. Now I want to share my feelings and emotions about Jack London's "Martin Eden". My opinion can differentiate from others, but still I am true to it.

Firstly, I want to make a brief review of the novel. *Martin Eden* is about a low class guy, who falls in love with a girl from elite. In order to get to the same level as her he tries to get self-education using all the tools in libraries. Ruth, the name of Martin's love, tries to help him to be the same as people in her society. She teaches him to basic laws of linguistic. Because of Martin's passion to the education and poetry he becomes educated and aware of things that are "hidden" in Ruth's society. Then the main character of the novel starts to write poems that are foolish and meaningless in the eyes of Ruth. Martin tries so hard to prove that he is a good poet, but Ruth repeats it is best for him to earn money rather than wasting time for useless things.

Martin never gives up. He sends his works to all possible newspapers and journals even if his stories and poems were rejected.

All in all Martin gets rid of all the thoughts about making money by other ways rather than writing. He made a name for himself. He becomes a well-known poet and story writer whose poems and stories get published in famous newspapers over and over. But is Martin happy after all he achieved?

There are several main ideas in this novel.

Firstly, this novel about having passion in life. While reading this book a reader gains more and more motivation. Martin Eden, being poor sailor, never makes a step back. He works on his weaknesses, reads books he does not know exist - he does anything just to be the one he dreams of. Even after all the rejections he continues to write.

The second main idea is to be true to yourself. Martin after hundreds of negative feedbacks does not lose his faith in himself. Nothing can decrease his self-assessment. This is what makes him Martin Eden. He deeply believes that the hope

swarming in his soul is not in vain. Martin is passionate person who has no one to trust, but himself. Martin spends days, months, years for improvement. He writes, sends, writes, sends - he repeats his actions in hope to get something. And finally he climbs step by step up the mountain that he dreamed of for years. So whenever we try to achieve something it is really important to understand that not anything can be easily taken. It may take days, months, even years to be someone we dream about.

The third idea of "Martin Eden" is to love people the way they are. Martin falls in love with Ruth and devotes all his attention to being a worthy person for her. But what does he get in return? Ruth uses every single chance to change Martin's personality. It may seem that she loves him, she wants him to be better, educated, wealthy, but does she support him in doing what he loves? "Limited minds can recognize limitations only in others." Martin truly loves her, he never hides his feelings, he shares his poems with her. But his poems mean nothing to her. Ruth wants a strong rich man by her side, a man who meets all the standards of her high society. The most-given question of Martin Eden is "Why didn't you dare it before? When I hadn't a job? When I was starving? When I was just as I am now, as a man, as an artist, the same Martin Eden?" Here he shows that all we need is love - a person who loves us the way we are.

The last, but not least idea of the novel is not everything we aspire to can be truly ours. Martin always dreamt of being well-known, being rich, but when he got it was he happy? No! The life he aspired to, the wealth of which he cherished, the people he admired - everything that seemed to him a sweet dream turned out to be nonsense, everything that he strove for so long and diligently was not worth his losses, his spent forces, was not worth the passed way.

Martin Eden is a sad story of a sad man who lacks the capacity for happiness and who is astonished to find that artistic success is as compromised as any other kind. But there is a kind of thrill in tracing his progress from rags to riches to annihilation.

This novel is very realistic. There are too many Martin Edens in our world, people who try their best, who are starving, who are ready for losses just to become what they are not.

This book about life, about love, about success, popularity, wealthiness - anything that is important for living. But can everyone survive without one of them or with all? Martin is an example of a person who cannot live with all of them. It is too much for him to be rich, famous, loved. Finally he feels unhappy. He has anything he needs to be happy, but he is not. So another lesson we can learn is to be grateful. Yes, we can be grateful and ask for more. But it is wrong to think that if we are not like this or like this, people will not accept us. We are perfect the way we are, and nothing deserves our piece of mind. If it takes away our piece, so it is worthless.

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